

DOI: 10.17323/2587-814X.2025.4.54.67

Systemic digitalization of economic mechanisms: A methodological approach

Sergey I. Parinov

E-mail: sparinov@gmail.com

Central Economic and Mathematical Institute of RAS, Moscow, Russia

Abstract

Modern IT and AI solutions open new opportunities for the digitalization of economic mechanisms, which leads to increased efficiency and contributes to business digital transformation processes. This article presents a methodological approach based on design principles from the “Institutional Analysis and Development” framework, which allows for the design of information processes underlying the coordination and governance functions of economic mechanisms. On this basis, an initial version of a concept for systemic digitalization of economic mechanisms has been developed, including a description of a multi-agent platform in the spirit of massively multiplayer online games, which ensures data collection and integration, analytical modeling, and support for coordination and decision-making in complex organizational-economic systems. The proposed approach to systemic digitalization of mechanisms based on IT/AI solutions represents a development of business informatics methods for optimizing business processes, for designing information systems to support managerial decision-making and digital transformation of companies. Overall for the economy, this promises an increase in the marginal productivity of business process participants, reduction of their losses, enhancement of business adaptive capabilities, and, as a result, an increase in the average efficiency of the economy. Based on the proposed concept, a “social order” for the IT/AI industry has been formed, which defines key needed solutions for mechanisms digitalization with expected high positive socio-economic effect.

Keywords: digitalization, economic mechanisms, business informatics, multi-agent modeling, artificial intelligence, decision support systems, digital transformation

Citation: Parinov S.I. (2025) Systemic digitalization of economic mechanisms: A methodological approach. *Business Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 54–67. DOI: 10.17323/2587-814X.2025.4.54.67

Introduction

The digitalization of economic processes and widespread implementation of IT/AI solutions are key factors in the contemporary development of the economy [1–6]. However, despite the active spread of digital tools, their integration into mechanisms of coordination and regulation of economic activity remains fragmented and methodologically heterogeneous [7–9]. In most cases, digital technologies are used to automate individual operations [1, 10], whereas systemic improvement of the efficiency of the entire set of economic mechanisms requires a fundamentally different approach – one that takes into account the general patterns of functioning of these mechanisms and allows for designing their digital transformation as a holistic process.

The aim of the proposed research is to improve the methodology of systemic digitalization of economic mechanisms to enhance their efficiency. It is assumed that such a methodology will be useful for forming an effective IT/AI platform for conducting systemic digitalization of regulatory mechanisms of various types used in the economy.

The scientific foundation of this research is connected with institutional analysis of joint activity and the concept of economic mechanisms as tools that allow business process participants to coordinate their actions and extract joint benefits. The use of the concept of “economic mechanism” (EM), which is the object of this research, is based on works [11–15]. According to these works, EMs arise and operate as a result of certain specific regulatory activities of people, which use: (a) established common rules; (b) formed skills; and (c) IT in the broad sense. In this case,

EMs include network structures [16–18], hierarchical organizations [19, 20], markets [15, 17], common rules of behavior taken into account by people, as well as institutions in the role of regulatory structures [14, 21–23].

The methodology of the proposed approach is based on the content of the “Institutional Analysis and Development” (IAD) framework [14, 24]. From the principles of institutional design in IAD, it follows that a large number of EMs are based on six universal functions that determine the coordination of joint activity, as well as its stability and adaptability to occurring changes [25]. The content of the six universal functions of EMs allows for defining typical information processes that ensure the operation of mechanisms. These information processes are considered as objects for EM digitalization. The use of various IT/AI solutions for their digitalization affects EM efficiency in different ways. The concept of EM efficiency introduced in [25] allows for analyzing IT/AI solutions from the point of view of their impact on EM efficiency. The set of selected IT/AI solutions that positively affect EM efficiency is proposed to be considered as a digital platform capable of effectively supporting coordination and governance of joint activity in various organizational and institutional contexts.

Thus, the research tasks include: (a) description of information processes that implement universal EM functions and general analysis of their impact on EM efficiency; (b) analysis of possible IT/AI solutions providing effective execution of EM information processes, which can be considered as the first version of a concept for systemic EM digitalization; (c) analysis of possible economic consequences from practical implementation of the systemic EM digitalization concept,

including highlighting part of the concept as a “social order” for the IT/AI industry.

A key feature of the proposed approach is its orientation toward applied multi-agent modeling and agent-oriented architectures. Such architecture allows, by analogy with virtual worlds of massively multiplayer online games, to represent participants of an economic system as active agents interacting in a dynamic environment, and to support their coordination taking into account changes in external and internal conditions.

The proposed approach contributes to the development of business informatics methods for optimizing business processes, and for designing information systems to support managerial decision-making and digital transformation of companies. This approach creates a methodological basis for integrating disparate digital solutions into a unified architecture. The resulting software platform can adapt to various types of joint activity, from collaboration and cooperation within companies to interaction in complex ecosystems. This creates additional conditions for deeper and more productive use of AI in governance and management, reducing transaction costs and accelerating decision-making processes.

The methodological and practical significance of the research lies in the fact that it unites institutional analysis, EM theory, and modern IT/AI technologies into a unified conceptual model applicable for designing digital platforms. This allows us to consider the proposed approach as a step toward forming a meta-mechanism of digitalization that regulates activities for creating and developing specific EMs and ensures their coordinated functioning in the digital environment.

The approximate scale of possible practical effect from implementing this approach can be estimated from survey results of managers and engineers in the aerospace industry. It is noted that in large complex projects, actions related to coordination take approximately 69% of an engineer’s time [26, p. 83]. The same source provides an estimate that due to coordination problems, project implementation time increases by at least 20–30%. It can be assumed that increased effi-

ciency of mechanisms as a result of automating some of their functions based on IT/AI solutions can obviously significantly reduce the share of managers’ costs attributed to coordination, as well as decrease time and resource losses in implementing large and complex projects.

1. Information processes and efficiency of economic mechanisms

In accordance with general concepts about the purpose of EMs, their functions should allow participants of joint activity (JA) to determine the content of their individual activity. When determining the content of JA, it is necessary, as far as possible taking into account bounded rationality and cognitive abilities of individuals, to consider the capabilities and intentions of all participants, as well as other factors significant for JA. Obviously, such functions correspond to the widespread understanding of the coordination process in EMs.

The content of JA and the coordination process itself are subject to various unpredictable changes. Thus, in addition to providing coordination, mechanisms must have functions for adapting to occurring changes. In order to ensure sustainable benefit receipt, such adaptation should include changing the content of participants’ individual activities, i.e., the possibility of re-coordinating JA. Adaptation should also allow changing the mechanism’s design itself. Such a set of functions additional to coordination corresponds to the generally accepted understanding of the governance process in a mechanism.

The principles of institutional design in IAD, which are the result of generalizing the reasons why some institutions (in the role of EMs) turn out to be successful and sustainable while others do not [14, p. 652], allow for specifying the set of functions implementing coordination and governance processes of EMs. In work [25], based on IAD design principles, a set of six universal EM functions was proposed that determine coordination and governance processes of JA. These functions can be considered universal for differ-

ent types of mechanisms, since they are derived based on IAD’s concepts of “universal building blocks” that underlie “social interactions in markets, hierarchies, families, sports, legislatures, elections, and other situations” [14, p. 5].

Figure 1 shows the scheme of connections between EM functions and corresponding information processes proposed in [25]. Information processes of coordination and governance represent a sequence of collection, processing, and use of information to obtain the maximum possible benefit under conditions of unpredictable changes.

In accordance with Fig. 1, to implement coordination, EM information processes must provide participants with opportunities and means of accounting for factors significant for JA, including information distributed among them. This requires participants to make efforts and use certain means for collecting and processing information necessary for collective

choice. The information obtained in this way is analyzed, which involves playing out possible interaction scenarios. For example, in the form of mental simulation of possible actions. In the course of such playing out, participants evaluate the assumed benefit from various JA variants, as well as associated costs, including mechanism costs. Based on the estimates obtained, participants can (for example, by enumeration method and/or using heuristics) select the preferred content of JA and coordinate final decisions about the content of their individual activity.

To implement governance, corresponding information processes in EMs must support the fixation of participants’ responsibility for implementing coordinated JA, as well as organizing monitoring, which creates a feedback effect in the EM, allowing participants to identify and analyze discrepancies between expected and actual JA results. With fixed responsibility of JA participants, monitoring allows us to determine possible culprits and/or causes of identified deviations.

Fig. 1. Universal functions and information processes of EMs [25].

Information processes of the “sustainability” function are aimed at maintaining sustainability of benefit receipt from JA based on monitoring results, including using sanctions and conflict resolution mechanisms for this purpose.

For each of the six EM functions, as well as associated information processes, their impact on mechanism efficiency parameters can be determined. Efficiency parameters in this case are: (1) the magnitude of costs associated with the mechanism’s operation, which has the nature of transaction costs; and (2) the amount of benefit from JA regulated by the corresponding mechanism. Specific methods of implementing mechanism functions and corresponding information processes affect the formation of both mechanism costs and JA benefits. Consequently, it is possible to perform analysis of EM efficiency depending on methods of organizing information processes, including using various IT/AI solutions for this.

The magnitudes of costs and benefits associated with EMs have different natures. The work [25] substantiates the possibility of their formal comparison, which allows for analysis of mechanism efficiency based on mathematical models. However, for the purposes of this research, general estimates of the nature of the connection between information processes and the magnitude of mechanism costs and JA benefits are sufficient.

A description of information processes associated with implementing universal EM functions, as well as the nature of their impact on mechanism efficiency, is presented in *Table 1*.

The information processes of mechanism functions listed in the middle column of *Table 1* can be subjected to computer and/or algorithmic automation and digitalization. The general effect of this is a possible reduction in time and other resources required by JA participants to implement mechanism functions. Cost savings for performing each individual function contributes to reducing the total volume of mechanism costs, since costs are summed.

However, the increase in benefits due to increased completeness of accounting [27] is realized only if more

complete and accurate information obtained during implementation of the “accounting” function is fully used in performing the other coordination functions.

Generalizing the identified opportunities for increasing mechanism efficiency (the right column of *Table 1*), it can be concluded that practical realization of these opportunities requires IT/AI solutions with the following capabilities:

- ◆ reduction of time costs for information processing by JA participants;
- ◆ automated collection and updating of information about capabilities and intentions of JA participants, as well as its systematization;
- ◆ assistance to JA participants in analyzing possible variants of their JA, in determining the best variants, as well as in achieving agreement of all participants regarding the best JA variant for practical implementation;
- ◆ assistance to participants in analyzing deviations of actual JA implementation from expected, and also, if necessary, assistance in determining and implementing measures to maintain JA sustainability.

2. Digitalization of information processes of mechanisms

The effect of EM digitalization will be most noticeable when coordination and governance processes require organizing the exchange, processing, and analysis of large amounts of frequently updated and poorly structured information. This case corresponds to JA consisting of a large number of participants who are affected by regular unpredictable changes. Under such conditions, a large volume of dynamically changing information arises in the JA mechanism, which requires participants to promptly process and analyze data, as well as have sufficiently high decision-making speed. This example has direct relevance to reality, since under modern conditions the activities of many large corporations, as well as the economies of different countries, represent JA with such properties.

Tables 2 and *3* present a description of methods for implementing universal coordination and governance

Table 1.

Information processes and efficiency of economic mechanisms

Mechanism functions	Information process of the function	Opportunities for increasing function efficiency
1. Accounting	Collection and primary processing of information about factors important for joint activity, including information distributed among participants. Systematization of data on current conditions for JA.	a) Reduction of time for collecting and processing information. b) Improvement of organization of collected information. c) Creation of conditions for obtaining greater benefit through increasing the completeness of accounting for important factors.
2. Choosing	Simulation of implementation of possible JA variants in order to obtain estimates of expected costs and benefits for these variants. Selection of JA variants with the best estimates.	a) Reduction of time costs for improving the quality of searching for better variants. b) Increasing accuracy of estimates of expected costs and benefits.
3. Coordinating	Information and communication support for decision-making about JA content taking into account capabilities and intentions of all participants based on feedback.	a) Reduction of decision-making time. b) Increasing probability of finding the best solution variant.
4. Accountability	Information support for fixing responsibility for implementing coordinated JA and for transferring JA to actual implementation mode.	a) Reduction of time costs for analyzing possible violations. b) Increasing flexibility and adaptability of adopted accountability to occurring changes.
5. Monitoring	Similar to the "accounting" function. Additionally – collection of information about actual JA implementation, as well as changes in conditions for JA.	a) Reduction of time costs for collecting and analyzing actual information. b) Increasing completeness and depth of the change tracking process.
6. Sustainability	Similar to "choice" + "coordination" functions. Additionally – use of feedback for changes in parameters of the used mechanism.	a) Reduction of time costs for determining the composition of required changes and for decision-making. b) Increasing the size of total benefit from JA.

functions based on IT/AI solutions. For each universal function in these tables, the following are briefly presented: (1) the goal of digitalization, (2) the general current state of digitalization of this function, (3) requirements for digitalization arising from the goal, (4) the possible role of AI in digitalizing the corresponding function. Since digitalization of all universal mechanism functions promises to reduce costs associated with the mechanism's operation, including par-

ticipants' time costs (costs for creating IT/AI solutions are not considered in this case), to avoid repetition this general point for all functions is excluded from the descriptions below but is implied. Questions of integrating the IT/AI solutions discussed below with existing business process management systems, including personnel management, sales, production, marketing, finance, etc., are beyond the scope of this article.

Table 2 presents digitalization of coordination information processes. Its general goal is to reduce participants' costs in determining JA content and increase the completeness of accounting for important factors, which increases the probability of obtaining maximum benefit.

Digitalization of governance information processes, presented in *Table 3*, is in turn aimed at reducing costs for maintaining sustainable receipt of maximum benefit and increasing adaptability to changes.

Practical implementation of digitalization of EM coordination and governance functions is expected to lead to:

1. General reduction of time and resource costs associated with mechanism operation.
2. Increasing completeness of accounting for factors important for JA and possible growth of benefit from JA.
3. Increasing adaptability of JA participants to the flow of unpredictable changes and growth of total benefit from JA over time.

All considered IT/AI solutions correspond to modern directions of technology development and theoretically can be created.

The descriptions presented above of interconnected IT/AI solutions, which are the embodiment of the methodology proposed for this research, can be considered as an initial version of a concept for systemic EM digitalization. This concept certainly requires deepening, development, and additional substantiation. However, in its current content, parts can already be identified whose practical embodiment is important and therefore requires special attention.

One of the key IT/AI solutions for effective mechanism digitalization, which has not yet been developed, is the implementation of agent-based simulation models on the basis of online platforms of the type of massively multiplayer online games' virtual worlds. In such virtual worlds, JA participants and other objects related to JA are represented by their digital twins [28, 29] and

have opportunities for intra-model interactions. Such a simulation model with capabilities for intra-model interactions offers users means of collective modeling for the purpose of analyzing and selecting scenarios of possible joint actions, including using algorithms for searching for variants of JA optimal for all participants in terms of benefit/cost ratios.

Another missing key solution is the integration of AI with an agent-based simulation model of the type described above, on the basis of which AI interacts with JA participants as:

- a) coordinator-mediator who helps JA participants coordinate parameters of their activities, as well as simplify decision-making about how to adapt parameters of their activities to occurring or planned changes;
- b) assistant arbiter for determining signs of violation of coordinated JA content and identification of presumed violators;
- c) control-analytical agent who monitors actual implementation of coordinated activity, analyzes and predicts deviations of actual JA results from expected, performs diagnosis of causes and forms proposals for corrections in JA parameters.

The two noted key applications are proposed to be included in the initial content of a "social order" for the IT/AI industry. Creating such applications would facilitate beginning work on designing and practically constructing an online platform offering users services for building EMs for a large number of types of JA.

3. Possible economic effect from mechanism digitalization

Let us assume that the IT/AI solutions described in *Tables 2* and *3* will be implemented in the future and digitalization of information processes of JA mechanisms of the type described above will become possible. Let us consider possible economic effects from using mechanisms with digitalization in the spirit of the proposed solutions.

Table 2.

Digitalization of coordination information processes

1. Accounting	
Goal	Increasing completeness of accounting through expanding scale (increasing number of participants) and deepening accounting (collecting maximum volume of important information).
Current State	Existing online platforms (Amazon, Facebook, Google, and others) already provide virtual space for digital communications and formation of digital twins of users. There are examples of using AI for searching and hiring employees (Unilever ¹ and Electrolux ²).
Requirements	Conduct dialogue with JA participants to update information about their capabilities and intentions for obtaining benefit from JA.
Role of AI	Proactive AI service with personal settings conducts dialogue with JA participants, collects information about their capabilities and intentions, creates and updates digital twins of participants. Machine learning improves accounting quality through analysis of communication patterns and prediction of participants' intentions.
2. Choice	
Goal	Improving the quality of searching for better JA variants and increasing accuracy of estimates of expected costs and benefits.
Current State	Computer and simulation modeling is widely used to reduce costs in selecting optimal activity variants ³ .
Requirements	Development of agent-based simulation modeling methods in the spirit of massively multiplayer online games, including representation of agents based on digital twins with the possibility of dynamic parameter changes, built-in means for intra-model user communications, etc.
Role of AI	AI integrated into the model improves computer experiment results, clarifies participants' capabilities and intentions through dialogue, evaluates possibilities for practical JA implementation.
3. Coordination	
Goal	Improving the quality of the procedure for determining the best JA variant for actual implementation by all participants.
Current State	CRM, ERP, PM, and BPMS systems exist. There are examples of using AI to optimize supply chains and coordinate processes in industry ⁴ .
Requirements	Development of means for collective playing out and coordination by JA participants in a simulation agent model of their JA content.
Role of AI	AI performs functions of: (a) a coordinator and collects proposals for correcting JA variants, demonstrates estimates of benefits and costs; (b) a mediator for resolving problems and finding compromises in individual dialogue with each participant; (c) analyst for determining potential conflicts and coordinating corrections of tasks and deadlines, competing goals and problem resolution strategies.

¹ <https://bernardmarr.com/the-amazing-ways-how-unilever-uses-artificial-intelligence-to-recruit-train-thousands-of-employees/>

² <https://www.phenom.com/resource/electrolux-group-digitalizes-processes-hiring-edge>

³ <https://www.anylogic.com/manufacturing/>

⁴ <https://serafai.com/blog/smart-manufacturing-case-studies/>

Table 3.

Digitalization of governance information processes

4. Accountability	
Goal	Increasing flexibility of fixing participants' accountability (contracting) and adaptability to unpredictable changes (smart contracting).
Current State	Many contracting methods exist, mainly as psychological and behavioral techniques, as well as legal recommendations.
Requirements	In the simulation model, the roles and accountability of each participant must be "transparently" defined, including display of the current stage of JA implementation and possible sanctions, predictions of violations and analysis of consequences with the ability to play out risk scenarios.
Role of AI	Analysis and forecasting of threats, surveying participants regarding understanding of accountability. AI acts as an assistant "arbiter" in case of violations, analyzes behavior history, predicts conflicts and proposes preventive measures. Can generate smart contracts and integrate with blockchain for immutable records of obligations.
5. Monitoring	
Goal	Increasing completeness of tracking JA implementation, reducing costs for comparing actual and expected results. Increasing speed and accuracy of obligation fulfillment analysis.
Current State	Methods for monitoring organizational activities exist. There is an example of using AI for monitoring factory condition (SIEMENS ⁵).
Requirements	Development of model algorithms in the role of control-analytical tool: (a) collection of information about actual JA implementation and environmental changes; (b) model analysis and prediction of deviations; (c) diagnosis of causes and their classification to determine corrections; (d) notification of participants about situations requiring attention.
Role of AI	Dynamic tracking of deviations, assessment of threats and risks. AI identifies unusual situations and patterns indicating problems or opportunities. Informs participants about changes requiring corrections.
6. Sustainability	
Goal	Minimizing losses from unpredictable changes and bringing total benefit closer to maximum possible values.
Current State	Methods exist for rapid organizational response to environmental changes and adaptation of business models.
Requirements	When sustainability is violated, model algorithms transfer participants to performing mechanism functions, starting with the "choosing" function. Support for practical implementation of the adaptation plan is needed with demonstration of the best scenarios in the simulation model.
Role of AI	Analysis of sustainability violations based on monitoring data, development of effective responses and list of individual actions for participants. AI can propose changes to the JA mechanism design to increase sustainability and performs the role of coordinator-mediator when adapting to changed conditions.

⁵ <https://www.siemens.com/global/en/products/automation/topic-areas/industrial-ai/usecases/ai-based-predictive-maintenance.html>

Cost reduction

Automating the performance of mechanism functions allows us to save time, effort, and other resources of participants which have the nature of transaction costs. As surveys show, coordination processes in the activities of engineers in complex modern productions take approximately 69% of time, and coordination problems increase project implementation time by at least 20-30% [26, p. 83]. The proposed automation of mechanism functions based on IT/AI solutions can reduce time losses several-fold, in particular, in engineers' work and in project implementation processes as a whole.

Benefit increase

Mechanism digitalization creates conditions for increasing benefit from JA in different ways:

- ◆ An analogy can be drawn with the growth of efficiency of physical mechanisms, in which reducing friction losses increases the amount of energy that can be spent on "useful" work. In the same way, reducing EM costs means increasing "free" time of JA participants, which can be spent by participants on obtaining various types of benefits. Increasing "free" time in itself can be considered as increasing the total benefit of JA participants.
- ◆ Increasing benefit with an increase in the number of JA participants due to deepening their specialization and division of labor. Growth in the number of participants usually significantly increases volumes of processed information and associated mechanism costs. Automation of mechanism functions can prevent growth of mechanism costs with an increase in the number of JA participants. Thus, conditions arise in the economy to involve more participants in JA and obtain additional benefit from this.
- ◆ Since digitalization increases volumes of information that can be collected and processed without significant cost growth, benefit from JA can grow as a result of expanding the area of choice of possible variants of JA content, as well as due to more complete accounting for capabilities and intentions of JA partici-

pants. In addition, improving sustainability of benefit receipt by participants under conditions of regular unpredictable changes means maximizing total benefit over time.

Increasing mechanism efficiency

Reduction of mechanism costs and increase in JA participants' benefits created by digitalization lead to growth in EM efficiency. This, in turn, obviously creates conditions for increasing the overall marginal productivity of JA participants. Increasing mechanism efficiency has a systemic and comprehensive impact on all JA processes. In this case, unlike the results of Acemoglu's analysis [1], productivity growth due to the use of IT/AI solutions can be expected in workplaces of all types. These same factors can lead to a decrease in the economy's need for managers.

The digitalization of EMs has a different nature of impact on JA than automation of final product production processes, which often leads to job cuts and increased inequality [1]. Unlike the consequences of traditional automation, when most of the benefit obtained from it accumulated with owners and managers of firms [1], digitalization of joint activity mechanisms and the associated growth in mechanism efficiency affects approximately equally all participants and workplaces of all types, causing growth in workers' marginal productivity.

Increasing mechanism efficiency can be a way to neutralize negative economic consequences associated with the observed growth in uncertainty and intensity of unpredictable changes due to acceleration of scientific and technological progress and other factors. The higher the intensity of unpredictable changes, the more often participants use mechanisms to adapt parameters of their JA to new conditions. This leads to growth in costs associated with using mechanisms, which can be compensated by automating mechanism functions. Unpredictable changes can also create new opportunities for increasing benefit, where the effectiveness of use is higher, the higher the EM efficiency.

Increasing adaptability

Improvement as a result of digitalization of mechanisms' abilities to support sustainable benefit receipt in the flow of unpredictable changes means increasing adaptive capabilities of all economic actors – from individual JA participants to the country's economy as a whole. The consequence of this can be smoothing in the economy of the amplitude of cost growth associated with “shock waves” of mass adaptation to changes, and increasing the “degree” of average normal intensity of changes in the economy.

Conclusion

The main result of this work is a contribution to the development of methodology for systemic digitalization of EMs based on IAD institutional design principles. This methodology in its current state includes: (a) an approach for identifying and describing a system of interconnected information processes implementing universal EM functions; (b) conceptual determination of EM efficiency parameters; (c) an approach for analyzing the impact of IT/AI solutions implementing EM information processes on EM efficiency parameters. As a test of this methodology, a description of general requirements for digitalization of EM information processes associated with increasing mechanism efficiency has been carried out. IT/AI solutions have been considered that allow, in the process of digitalizing information processes in EMs, to achieve increased mechanism efficiency. The IT/AI solutions obtained in this way are proposed to be considered as an initial version of a concept for systemic EM digitalization. An analysis of possible economic consequences of EM digitalization has been conducted. In the content of the concept, necessary but currently missing key solutions for systemic EM digitalization have been identified, which are proposed to be considered as a “social order” for the IT/AI industry.

Scientific novelty of the results obtained is provided by the development of scientific concepts about a system of sequentially interconnected information

processes implementing universal EM functions that gradually create conditions for effective functioning of mechanisms. The proposed methodology allows us to organize selection of both existing IT/AI solutions and development of requirements for currently missing solutions that are necessary for systemic EM digitalization in order to increase their efficiency.

The practical significance of the results obtained is associated with the expected positive impact of EM digitalization both at the level of individual businesses and on the economy as a whole, since digitalization promises significant positive changes at both microeconomic and macroeconomic levels. Positive expectations associated with EM digitalization can form motivations in the IT/AI industry for developing required solutions. The content of the proposed “social order” can, in this case, indicate to IT/AI developers work directions and describe general specifications for required solutions.

The research we carried out makes a certain contribution to the current discussion in scientific literature of the possibilities of modern IT/AI solutions for digitalization and automation of diverse socio-economic activities [1–6]. This work differs from and complements these studies in that it proposes analysis of individual aspects of the impact of IT/AI solutions on EMs, through which these innovations affect practically all economic actors. Increasing EM efficiency with the help of IT/AI solutions is expected to lead to increased marginal productivity of practically all workers employed in the economy, which some authors indicate as one of the most important requirements for implementing AI technologies [1, p. 45].

Taking into account the expected positive socio-economic effect from EM digitalization, directions for further research include development and empirical testing of the proposed methodology, as well as creation on the basis of this methodology of modeling tools for computer analysis of practical recommendations for modernizing EM functioning. ■

Acknowledgments

The work was carried out within the framework of the State Assignment of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation on two topics. Development of the concept of systemic digitalization of economic mechanisms was carried out on the topic “Software-analytical complexes for improving the efficiency of management decisions made in the Russian Federation” No. FMGF-2025-0001, No.

EGISU NIOKTR 125031003392-3. Methodology development was carried out within the framework of the topic “Research and development of tools for developing a unified and secure environment for scientific cooperation for economic research within the framework of Open Science as part of the digital economy” No. FMGF-2022-0010, No. EGISU NIOKTR 124022000041-2.

References

1. Acemoglu D. (2025) The simple macroeconomics of AI. *National Bureau of Economic Research*, Working Paper No. 32487. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32487>
2. Agrawal A., Gans J.S., Goldfarb A. (2023) Artificial intelligence adoption and system-wide change. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, vol. 33(2), pp. 327–337. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jems.12521>
3. Bick A., Blandin A., Deming D. (2025) The impact of generative AI on work productivity. *St. Louis Fed On the Economy*. Available at: <https://www.stlouisfed.org/on-the-economy/2025/feb/impact-generative-ai-work-productivity> (accessed 25 November 2025).
4. Goldman Sachs (2023) *Generative AI could raise global GDP by 7 percent*. Available at: <https://www.goldmansachs.com/intelligence/pages/generative-ai-could-raise-global-gdp-by-7-percent.html> (accessed 25 November 2025).
5. Korinek A., Suh D. (2024) Scenarios for the transition to AGI. *National Bureau of Economic Research*, Working Paper No. 32255. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32255>
6. Chui M., Hazan E., Roberts R., et al. (2023) The economic potential of generative AI: The next productivity frontier. *McKinsey & Company*. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/the-economic-potential-of-generative-ai-the-next-productivity-frontier> (accessed 25 November 2025).
7. Chen M., Martins T.S., Zhang L., Dong H. (2025) Digital transformation in project management: A systematic review and research agenda. *Systems*, vol. 13(8), article 625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/systems13080625>
8. Badasjane V., Ahlskog M., Granlund A., Bruch J., Sauter B. (2024) Navigating through uncertainties: coordinating digital transformation in international manufacturing networks. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, vol. 36(9), pp. 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jmtm-06-2024-0322>
9. Vigoda-Gadot E., Mizrahi S. (2024) The digital governance puzzle: Towards integrative theory of humans, machines, and organizations in public management. *Technology in Society*, vol. 77, article 102530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102530>
10. Dizikes P. (2024) Daron Acemoglu: What do we know about the economics of AI? *MIT News*, Available at: <https://economics.mit.edu/news/daron-acemoglu-what-do-we-know-about-economics-ai> (accessed 25 November 2025).

11. Hurwicz L. (1973) The design of mechanisms for resource allocation. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 63(2), pp. 1–30.
12. Hurwicz L., Reiter S. (2006) *Designing economic mechanisms*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511754258>
13. Maskin E., Sjöström T. (2002) Chapter 5 Implementation theory. *Handbook of social Choice and Welfare*, vol. 1, pp. 237–288. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0110\(02\)80009-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0110(02)80009-1)
14. Ostrom E. (2005) *Understanding institutional diversity*. Princeton University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt7s7wm>
15. Williamson O.E. (1975) *Markets and hierarchies: Analysis and antitrust implications*. New York: Free Press.
16. Granovetter M. (1983) The strength of weak ties: A network theory revisited. *Sociological theory*, vol. 1, pp. 201–233. <https://doi.org/10.2307/202051>
17. Powell W.W. (1990) Neither market nor hierarchy: Network forms of organization. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, vol. 12, pp. 295–336.
18. Provan K.G., Kenis P. (2008) Modes of network governance: Structure, management, and effectiveness. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, vol. 18(2), pp. 229–252. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum015>
19. Malone T.W., Crowston K. (1994) The interdisciplinary study of coordination. *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 26(1), pp. 87–119. <https://doi.org/10.1145/174666.174668>
20. Weigand H., van der Poll F., de Moor A. (2003) Coordination through communication. Proceedings of the 8th International Working Conference on the Language-Action Perspective on Communication Modeling (LAP 2003) (eds. H. Weigand, G. Goldkuhl, A. de Moor), Tilburg University Press, pp. 115–134.
21. Coase R. (1998) The new institutional economics. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 88(2), pp. 72–74.
22. North D.C. (1995) The new institutional economics and third world development. *The New Institutional Economics and Third World Development* (eds. J. Harriss, J. Hunter, and C. M. Lewis), Taylor & Francis Group, pp. 17–26.
23. Williamson O.E. (2000) The new institutional economics: Taking stock, looking ahead. *Journal of Economic Literature*, vol. 38(3), pp. 595–613. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.38.3.595>
24. Lara A. (2015) Rationality and complexity in the work of Elinor Ostrom. *International Journal of the Commons*, vol. 9(2), pp. 573–594. <https://doi.org/10.18352/ijc.468>
25. Parinov S.I. (2025) Mechanisms of socio-economic activity based on the principles of institutional design: the search for a general model. *Economic Sociology*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 38–66 (in Russian).
26. Crabtree R.A., Fox M.S., Baid N.K. (1997) Case studies of coordination activities and problems in collaborative design. *Research in Engineering Design*, vol. 9, pp. 70–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01596483>
27. Hayek F.A.V. (1945) The use of knowledge in society. *The American Economic Review*, vol. 35(44), pp. 518–530.

28. Makarov V.L., Bakhtizin A.R., Beklaryan G.L. (2019) Developing digital twins for production enterprises. *Business Informatics*, vol. 13(4), pp. 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1998-0663.2019.4.7.16>
29. Telnov Yu.F., Kazakov V.A., Danilov A.V. (2024) Designing a multi-agent system for a network enterprise. *Business Informatics*, vol. 18(3), pp. 70–86. <https://doi.org/10.17323/2587-814X.2024.3.70.86>

About the author

Sergey I. Parinov

Doctor of Sciences (Technology), Candidate of Sciences (Economics);

Chief Researcher, Central Economic and Mathematical Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 47 Nakhimovsky Ave., Moscow 117418, Russia;

E-mail: sparinov@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-8333-2657